

<https://doi.org/10.70590/ice.2025.01.99>

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:8ECEC48B-2700-47AF-9D7E-98B377379903>

● Hidden new species in large city, *Simulatacalles yuexiuensis* sp. nov. from Guangzhou, Guangdong, China (Coleoptera, Curculionidae, Cryptorhynchinae, Cryptorhynchini)

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Abstract: *Simulatacalles yuexiuensis* sp. nov. is described from Guangzhou, Guangdong, China, and its key morphological characters are illustrated. A modified key to species of the genus is provided after re-examination of specimens of most species in this genus. Photographs of habitus of all congeners except *Simulatacalles oshimaensis* Morimoto & Miyakawa, 1985 are also presented.

Keywords: China, Curculionidae, Cryptorhynchini, Guangzhou, new species

● 隐藏在大城市中的新物种，中国广东省广州市的越秀惜象（鞘翅目，象虫科，隐喙象亚科，隐喙象族）

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摘要: 本文描述了产自中国广东省广州市的新物种——越秀惜象 (*Simulatacalles yuexiuensis* sp. nov.)，对它的重要形态特征进行了图示说明。在重新检视该属大部分物种的标本后，我们给出了该属新的分种检索表。文中还提供了该属除大岛惜象 *Simulatacalles oshimaensis* Morimoto & Miyakawa, 1985 外其它物种的整体形态图。

本研究隶属于广州市越秀区林业和园林局的越秀区野生动植物资源本底调查(项目编号: FCZ2024-5039)。

关键词: 中国，象虫科，隐喙象族，广州，新种

Citation: Zhu J & Ye Z 2025: Hidden new species in large city, *Simulatacalles yuexiuensis* sp. nov. from Guangzhou, Guangdong, China (Coleoptera, Curculionidae, Cryptorhynchinae, Cryptorhynchini). *The Indochina Entomologist*, 1 (99): 1031–1045. [朱江 & 叶蓁 2025: 隐藏在大城市中的新物种，中国广东省广州市的越秀惜象（鞘翅目，象虫科，隐喙象亚科，隐喙象族）。中南半岛昆虫学家, 1 (99): 1031–1045.

<https://doi.org/10.70590/ice.2025.01.99>

Accepted by Cheng-Bin WANG: 18.XII.2025; published online: 19.XII.2025

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● Introduction

Katsura Morimoto (1978) established *Simulatacalles* as an independent genus, separated from *Acalles* described by Schönherr (1825), with *Acalles simulator* Roelofs, 1875 as the type species. The former can be differentiated from the latter by frons width and metepisternal sutures (Morimoto 1978). Subsequently, *S. oshimaensis* Morimoto & Miyakawa, 1985, *S. wantanabei* Morimoto & Miyakawa, 1985, *S. pustulosus* Morimoto & Lee, 1992 were described and placed within the genus. The genus currently is known to comprise these four species, which are distributed in South Korea, Japan and China (Taiwan). (Hong et al. 2011; Morimoto & Miyakawa 1985; Morimoto & Lee 1992; Morimoto 1978).

From October 2024 to September 2025, we conducted a preliminary survey of insect community diversity in urban green spaces of Yuexiu District, Guangzhou City, Guangdong province, southern China. In the study, more than 1,000 specimens were collected in total, among which several are considered potential new species, one of which is described herein.

● Material and methods

All specimens of the new species were collected by a sifter (net diameter 5 mm × 5 mm), which is used to separate all the leaf litter. All sieved residue was stored in breathable cotton bags and carefully labelled with the plot-number. After bringing the samples back to the State Environmental Protection Key Laboratory, we used a modified heating dryer to separate insects from leaf litter. Specimens were relaxed and softened in 40°C hot water for 24 hours, then cleaned by using an ultrasonic cleaning machine for 1 minute. Specimens were transferred to distilled water to be observe and dissect. In order to examine the genitalia, the abdomens were detached and treated with a 10% solution of potassium hydroxide (KOH) for 12 hours, then transferred to distilled water to flush the remaining KOH and stop any further bleaching. After examination, the body parts were mounted on a slide for further study. All photographs of the new species were taken using a Sigma FP-L camera with Mitutoyo BD PLAN APO 10X and Mitutoyo BD PLAN APO 20X. The final deep focus images were created with Helicon Focus 7.7.0 stacking software, and post-processed with Adobe Photoshop CC 2024. Collections cited in this paper are indicated by the following abbreviations:

SCIES: Insect Collection of South China Institute of Environmental Sciences, Guangzhou, China.

EUMJ: Collection of Ehime University Museum, Matsuyama, Japan.

● Taxonomy

Simulatacalles yuexiuensis sp. nov. 越秀惜象

<https://zoobank.org/8A4B8C7B-B9FF-4800-8799-E146CDEF041A>

Figs 1–4

Type material. Holotype: ♂ [SCIES], Yuexiu Park, Yuexiu District, Guangzhou city, Guangdong Prov., China, 24. III. 2025, Jiangzhu & Zhen-Yu Piao leg.

Paratypes. (2♂♂, 2♀♀, 3exs. [SCIES]): 1♂, 1♀, 2exs.: same data as holotype; 1♂, 1♀, 1 ex.: same data as holotype except 28. III. 2025.

Etymology. The specific epithet is from the Chinese name (Pinyin) of the type locality “Yuexiu Park”. The name is an adjective.

Holotype, male (Fig. 1; Fig. 2; Fig. 3 B, D-F; Fig. 4 E-H). Body length: 2.19mm. Body mostly shiny black; base of head and femora slightly lighter, rusty brown; antennae and tarsi with claws much lighter, reddish-brown. Entire body except elytra deeply punctured, each puncture bearing a yellowish scale. Elytra microwrinkled and

partly covered by white and orange prostrate scales, bearing 9 striae and intervals with shiny pustules. Head finely punctate except at the base of the parietals; punctures deeply depressed, each defined by a ridge, generally similar in size and shape over most of the surface but becoming fainter apically on the rostrum, each bearing a yellowish scale. Base of the parietals microwrinkled, with punctures sparse and faint. Rostrum strong, weakly curved downward, as wide at the apex as at the base, narrowed at the middle.

FIGURE 1. Habitus of *Simulatacalles yuexiuensis* sp. nov.: **A** dorsal view of habitus **B** lateral view of habitus **C** ventral view of habitus **D** ventral view of male genitalia **E** lateral view of male genitalia **F** dorsal view of male genitalia (holotype, male, Yuexiu, Guangdong, China).

Antennae pubescent, moderately long, inserted in the middle of rostrum. Scape approximately twice the combined length of the funicle and club, distinctly curved in its proximal half, gradually enlarged apically. Funicle 7-segmented; antennomeres 1–2 combined as long as antennomeres 3–6 combined; antennomeres 3–7 compressed, appearing as short cylinders. Club ovoid, as long as antennomeres 4–7 combined.

FIGURE 2. Body parts of *Simulatacalles yuexiuensis* sp. nov.: **A** anterior view of head **B** anterior view of right proleg **C** dorsal view of right middle leg **D** anterior view of left middle leg **E** dorsal view of right hind leg **F** anterior view of left hind leg (holotype, male, Yuexiu, Guangdong, China).

Pronotum slightly broader than long, widest at mid-length, hexagonal, constricted behind the anterior margin; anterior margin distinctly narrower than posterior margin. Surface finely punctate; punctures deeply depressed, each defined by a ridge and bearing a yellowish scale, becoming slightly smaller from center toward margins. A faint median carina present centrally, formed by the confluence of enlarged ridges from 2–3 punctures.

FIGURE 3. Body parts of *Simulatacalles yuexiuensis* sp. nov.: **A** anterior view of head **B** anterior view of right proleg **C** dorsal view of right middle leg **D** anterior view of left middle leg **E** dorsal view of right hind leg **F** anterior view of left hind leg (holotype, male, Yuexiu, Guangdong, China).

Elytra oval, 1.09× longer than wide, widest at the anterior third; sides regularly rounded. Surface partly covered with 5-10 patches of white and orange scales (partially detached in the dried specimen), and with 9 striae. Intervals bearing shiny pustules which are slightly longer than width; pustules along basal margin and in apical area slightly smaller than those on disc; each pustule bearing a brownish scale on its posterior slope. Interstriae nearly as wide as striae, each with approximately 10 small punctures. Scutellum absent.

FIGURE 4. Habitat and habitus in life of *Simulatacalles yuexiuensis* sp. nov.: A-D in leaf litter E-H habitus in life (holotype, male, Yuexiu, Guangdong, China).

Legs finely punctate; punctures deeply depressed, each defined by a ridge and bearing a yellowish scale. Femora unarmed, apically twisted and thickened. Tibiae slenderest at base, widening abruptly beyond the torsion, then gradually tapering toward apex; tibial spines arranged in two rows, approximately 8-10 in each row; apex densely covered with setae; mucro well-developed. Hind femur with a remarkable finely microwrinkled area apically on the internal aspect; the microwrinkles composed of precise, parallel striations.

Abdomen as long as wide. Ventrites 1+2 sparsely and coarsely punctate; ventrite 1 distinctly longer than 2; ventrites 1+2 combined slightly longer than ventrites 3+4+5 combined. All ventrites bearing yellowish scales. Suture between ventrites 1 and 2 moderately sinuous; remaining sutures straight and deeply impressed. Intercostal process of ventrite 1 slightly sinuous.

Male genitalia. Aedeagal body with sides subparallel in basal three-fourths, thence gradually and distinctly narrowing to a bluntly rounded apex, shorter than the median apodeme; evenly and moderately curved in lateral view. Tegmen Y-shaped, with tegmenal apodeme faintly curved at middle and base. Endophallus very long, moderately sclerotized medially and strongly sclerotized basally, bearing a basal cyclic sclerite.

Paratypes (Fig. 3A, C; Fig. 5A, B). Body length: 2.98–4.11 mm. Specimens conform essentially to the holotype in general morphology. An individual exhibits more developed pustules on the elytra, in which the distance between consecutive pustules is subequal to the length of a single pustule. The pronotal median carina varies from faint to distinctly developed.

Male genitalia of the two paratypes conform essentially to the holotype in general morphology.

FIGURE 5. Female genitalia of *Simulatacalles yuexiuensis* sp. nov. and *S. pustulosus*: **A** bursa copulatrix of *S. yuexiuensis* sp. nov. **B** abdominal sternite VIII of *S. yuexiuensis* sp. nov. **C** bursa copulatrix of *S. pustulosus* **D** abdominal sternite VIII of *S. pustulosus* (**A**, **B**: paratype, female, Yuexiu, Guandong, China **C**, **D**: same individual referred to Fig. 7). **Annotations:** Cr cornu Cl collum Ra ramus SpG spermathecal gland SV spiculum ventrale AL apical lobe.

Female genitalia (Fig. 5A, B) with abdominal sternite VIII bearing transversely aligned apical lobes having rounded sides and an apical margin bearing a small number of elongate, thin bristles. The spiculum ventrale, slender, twice the length of the apical lobe, with a thickened, straight base. Spermatheca falciform, with a moderately sclerotized ramus and a slender, twisted cornu, distinctly longer than the collum.

Diagnosis. The new species is generally readily distinguishable from its congeners except *S. pustulosus* by the following characters: (a) pronotum broader than long, broadest at the middle, strongly pustulate; (b) elytron black, with 9 striae; (c) intervals bearing shiny pustules, pustules smaller and oval at the bases and apices, slightly longer at central area; However, individuals with the most developed pustules can be difficult to separate from *S. pustulosus* specimens that exhibit the least developed pustulation (Fig. 9). The differences between them are listed in the table below.

Distribution. China (Guangdong).

Biology (Fig. 4A-D). All specimens were collected from the leaf litter layer in a mixed secondary broadleaved and bamboo forest. The forest is dominated by *Cinnamomum burmanni* (Lauraceae) as the constructive species, with associated species including *Ligustrum sinense* (Oleaceae), *Bambusa textilis* (Poaceae), *Falcataria falcata* (Fabaceae), *Cyclosorus parasiticus* (Thelypteridaceae), and *Pteris semipinnata* (Pteridaceae).

TABLE 1. Differential diagnosis between *S. pustulosus* and *S. yuexiuensis* sp. nov.

	<i>S. pustulosus</i>	<i>S. yuexiuensis</i> sp. nov.
Internal aspect of hind femur	Apical microwrinkled area with rough striations (Fig. 9A).	Apical microwrinkled area with parallel striations (Fig. 2F, Fig. 3F).
Punctures on rostrum	Punctures deeply depressed at base, weakening rapidly and sometimes almost entirely smooth, most lacking a clear ridge (Fig. 9A).	Almost entirely depressed, fainter apically, most defined by a ridge (Fig. 2A).
Punctures on pronotum	Various size (Fig. 9A).	Similar size (Fig. 3A-C).
Suture between ventrites 1 and 2	Straight, slightly sinuous at middle (Fig. 9B).	Moderately sinuous (Fig. 1C).
Bursa copulatrix	Spermatheca falciform, with a moderately sclerotized ramus and a slightly twisted cornu, thickened apically, slightly longer than the collum. (Fig. 5C)	Spermatheca falciform, with a moderately sclerotized ramus and a slender, twisted cornu, distinctly longer than the collum. (Fig. 5A)
Abdominal sternite VIII	The spiculum ventrale slender, 2.5 times the length of the apical lobe, with a round base. (Fig. 5D)	The spiculum ventrale, slender, 2 times length of the apical lobe, with a thickened, straight base. (Fig. 5B)

Simulatacalles simulator (Roelofs, 1875) 仿惜象

Figs 6; 9B

Material examined. 1 ex. [EUMJ], Nishiumi Town, Is. Kashima, Japan, 9. VI. 2001., M. Namba leg.; 1 ex. [EUMJ], Ozu. Nagahama-cho, Shiba, Japan, 30. VI. 2001., C. Takahashi leg., 1 ex. [EUMJ], Ozu. Nagahama-cho, Shiba, Japan, 6. V. 2001., M&A. Sakai leg.; 1 ex. [EUMJ], Nyuta-cho, Onzanji, Japan, 6. XI. 1993., M. Sakai leg. (in leaf litter); 1 ex. [EUMJ], Ozu. Goro. Riverside of Hiji-kawa, Japan, 30. VI. 2001., Sugiura & Ito leg. (in leaf litter); 1 ex. [EUMJ], Ozu. Goro. Riverside of Hiji-kawa, Japan, 31. VI. 2001., Ishikawa leg. (in leaf litter).

FIGURE 6. Habitus of *Simulatacalles simulator* with the origin label (Nishiumi Town, Is. Kashima, Japan, 9. VI. 2001., M. Namba leg.): **A** dorsal view of habitus **B** ventral view of habitus.

Notes. Our study is based on material previously identified by Xiao-Feng Li, an identification we have confirmed based on the following characts: (a) pronotum broader than long, broadest at the middle, with a few indefinite granules; (b) elytron black, with 9 striae; (c) intervals bearing shiny pustules, most pustules same in size and equidistant.

***Simulatacalles pustulosus* Morimoto & Lee 1992 瘤惜象**

Figs 5 C, D; 7; 9A

Material examined. 1 ♀. [EUMJ], Toon, Sunouchi, around Riv. Sodatani-gawa, Japan, 16. III. 2007, Yugo Sato leg. (Leaf litter of a bamboo grove); 1 ex. [EUMJ], Toon, Sunouchi, Wadamaru, Japan, 13. III. 2007, Yugo Sato leg. (Soil 30–50cm); 1 ex. [EUMJ], Nyuta-cho, Konji, Japan, 6.XI. 1993, M. Sakai leg. (in leaf litter); 1 ex. [EUMJ], Mt. Kasuga, Nara, Japan, 19. XI. 1989, M. Sakai leg.

FIGURE 7. Habitus of *Simulatacalles pustulosus* with the origin label (Toon, Sunouchi, around Riv. Sodatani-gawa, Japan, 16. III. 2007, Yugo Sato leg.): **A** dorsal view of habitus **B** ventral view of habitus.

Notes. We were unable to examine the type specimen as it is on loan since 2024. The specimens are characterized by the pronotum broader than long, broadest at the middle and strongly pustulate, as well as elytron with 9 striae and intervals bearing shiny pustules (smaller and oval at the bases and apices, much longer at central area). These characters assign them to this species.

Simulatacalles wantanabei Morimoto & Miyakawa, 1985 渡边氏惜象

Fig. 8

Material examined: 3 exs. [EUMJ], Kamijima-cho, Akahone-jima Is., Japan, 2. V. 2009., Yugo Sato leg.; 1 ex. [EUMJ], Nago, Haneji, NW of Mt. Tanodake, Japan, 25. X. 1987., Y. Nishikawa leg.; 1 ex. [EUMJ], Toon, Sunouchi, Wadamaru, Japan, 13. III. 2007., Yugo Sato leg. (soil 30-50cm).

FIGURE 8. Habitus of *Simulatacalles watanabei* with the origin label (Kamijima-cho, Akahone-jima Is., Japan, 2. V. 2009., Yugo Sato leg.): **A** dorsal view **B** ventral view.

Notes. The type specimen is on loan since 2024. We assign the specimens to this species based on these characters below: (a) pronotum as broad as long, broadest behind the middle, punctate, not tuberculate nor pustulate; (b) elytron black, with reddish-brown along the sutural area, with 9 striae; (c) intervals only with a few indefinite tubercles.

FIGURE 9. Hind femur of *Simulatacalles pustulosus* and *S. simulator*: **A** apex of hind femur of *S. pustulosus*, anterior view (same individual referred to Fig. 7) **B** apex of hind femur of *S. simulator*, anterior view (same individual referred to Fig. 6).

Revised Key to *Simulatacalles* Species (modified from Morimoto & Lee 1992)

- 1 (2) Elytron with 8 striae, the sixth stria obsolete; elytra more or less infused with reddish-brown.
.....*Simulatacalles oshimaensis* Morimoto & Miyakawa, 1985
- 2 (1) Elytron with 9 striae; elytra black or at most reddish-brown along the sutural area (Fig. 1A; Fig. 6A; Fig. 7A; Fig. 8A).
- 3 (4) Body elongate (Fig. 8); pronotum as long as broad (Fig. 8A); elytra reddish-brown along suture, at least pustules on interval 1 reddish (Fig. 8A); pronotum finely punctate, punctures subequal in shape and size from center to both margins (Fig. 8A); elytra with a patch of scales behind middle (Fig. 8A).....
.....*Simulatacalles wantanabei* Morimoto & Miyakawa, 1985
- 4 (3) Body oval (Fig. 1; Fig. 6; Fig. 7); pronotum broader than long (Fig. 1; Fig. 6; Fig. 7); elytra black (Fig. 1; Fig. 6; Fig. 7); pronotum finely punctate, punctures becoming slightly smaller from center toward both margins (Fig. 1; Fig. 6; Fig. 7).
- 5 (6) Hind femur without a distinct, finely microwrinkled area apically on internal aspect (Fig. 9B); intervals bearing shiny pustules, most pustules subequal in size and rounded in shape (Fig. 6A).....
.....*Simulatacalles simulator* (Roelofs, 1875)
- 6 (5) Hind femur with a distinct, finely microwrinkled area apically on internal aspect (Fig. 2F; Fig. 9A); intervals bearing shiny pustules, pustules variable in shape and size (Fig. 1A; Fig. 7A).
- 7 (8) Hind femur with a distinct, finely microwrinkled area apically on internal aspect, composed of rough striations (Fig. 9A); rostrum with punctures deeply depressed at base, most punctures lacking a clear ridge, weakening rapidly, most parts of surface sometimes smooth (Fig. 7A); intervals bearing shiny pustules, obviously longer than width (Fig. 7A); suture between ventrites 1 and 2 straight, slightly sinuous at middle (Fig. 7B). Distributed in Korea and Japan *Simulatacalles pustulosus* Morimoto & Lee 1992
- 8 (7) Hind femur with a distinct, finely microwrinkled area apically on internal aspect, composed of precise, parallel striations (Fig. 2F); punctures on rostrum deeply depressed, each defined by a ridge, generally similar in size and shape on most parts of surface, becoming fainter apically (Fig. 2A); intervals bearing shiny pustules, longer than width (Fig. 1A); suture between ventrite 1 and 2 moderately sinuous (Fig. 1C; Fig. 3D). Bisexual, distributed in Guangdong, China.....*Simulatacalles yuexiuensis* **sp. nov.**

● Discussion

The scale patches on elytra may possess taxonomic value. All type material of *Simulatacalles yuexiuensis* **sp. nov.** have similar scale patches when living (some individuals detached after being made into specimens), and can be used to distinguished from its congeners individuals which retained scale patches. Further documentation using ecological photographs in dorsal view maybe help for facilitate future taxonomic studies and enable rapid identification within this genus.

In recent years, several new insect species have been described from Guangzhou, including *Falsonannocerus haizhuensis* Zhu, Wang & Feng, 2021, *Eidoreus haizhuensis* Liu & Li, 2024, *Dichodontocis guangzhouensis* Xu & Li, 2024, *Acalyptomerus lawrencei* Liu, Yu & Li, 2025 and *Trachyphloeosoma rutiani* Zhu, Wang & Ye, 2025. These species were all discovered in urban parks and suburban areas, highlighting the ecological value of preserved green spaces for insect diversity conservation amidst urban development. Furthermore, these findings underscore that the insect fauna of even a major metropolis like Guangzhou remains inadequately documented, with many species likely yet to be discovery.

While the leaf litter in urban parks and suburbs supports high insect diversity, common horticultural practices often counteract conservation efforts. Excessive removal of this litter disrupts critical insect habitats. We therefore recommend limiting litter clearance and conducting comprehensive surveys to understand the composition of litter-

dwelling insect communities and their relationship with the environment, so as to formulate more targeted conservation strategies.

鞘翅上的鳞片斑可能具有分类学价值。所有越秀惜象的模式在制成标本前都有相似的鳞斑（部分个体在制成标本后脱落），并且能使用该特征将其与同属其它物种保留鳞斑的个体加以区分。通过拍摄背面角度的生态照片可能将促进该属未来的分类学研究，并实现物种的快速鉴定。

近年来，广州市陆续发表了一些新的昆虫物种，例如 *Falsonannocerus haizhuensis* Zhu, Wang & Feng, 2021、*Eidoreus haizhuensis* Liu & Li, 2024、*Dichodontocis guangzhouensis* Xu & Li, 2024、*Acalyptomerus lawrencei* Liu, Yu & Li, 2025 以及 *Trachyphloeosoma rutiani* Zhu, Wang & Ye, 2025。这些物种均发现于城市公园或近郊区域，凸显了在城市发展中保留绿地对昆虫多样性保护的生态价值。此外，这些发现也表明，即使是广州这样的特大城市，其昆虫多样性数据仍缺乏足够记录，很可能仍有较多物种有待发现。

公园及郊区的落叶层蕴藏着丰富的昆虫多样性，然而常规的园林管理措施却常与保护目标相悖。过度清扫落叶会破坏这些昆虫的关键栖息环境。因此，我们建议减少落叶清扫，并尽快启动详尽的调查研究，以深入了解落叶层栖息昆虫的群落构成及其与环境的关系，从而制定出有针对性的保护策略。

● Acknowledgements

We extend our sincere gratitude to Hiroyuki Yoshitomi (Ehime University Museum, Matsuyama, Japan) and Xiao-Feng Li (Ehime University, Matsuyama, Japan) for providing numerous photographs and valuable information, and to Ming-Yi Liang, Jia-Hua Dong, and Di-Wen Liang (South China Institute of Environmental Sciences, Guangzhou, China) for their assistance with the study.

We also wish to acknowledge Qing-Tian Li and Juan-Juan Luo (Yuexiu Park, Guangzhou, China) for their help and guidance in the field. The conducive environment resulting from the excellent park management at Yuexiu Park enabled the discovery of this species.

We extend our deepest gratitude to the Yuexiu Bureau of Forestry and Gardening, to whose initiation and facilitation this project is owed, and for their continuous and substantial support throughout our work.

我们由衷感谢 Hiroyuki Yoshitomi（爱媛大学博物馆）和李晓峰（爱媛大学）提供了大量的图像及珍贵资料。同时也感激梁明易、董家华、梁迪文（以上均为华南环境科学研究所）对我们工作的支持与帮助。

我们也要感谢李庆天，罗娟娟（广州市越秀公园）对我们的野外工作提供的帮助和指导。越秀公园的良好园林管理，使该物种的发现成为可能。

最后要特别感激广州市越秀区林业和园林局，正是他们促成了这个项目，并持续给予我们大量支持。

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● **Additional information**

Author contributions: Conceptualization: J Zhu. Resources: J Zhu & Z Ye. Supervision: Z Ye. Visualization: J Zhu. Writing - Original Draft: J Zhu. Writing - Review & Editing: J Zhu & Z Ye.

Conflict of interest: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Data availability: All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

Ethical statement: No ethical statement was reported.

Funding: Baseline Survey of Wildlife Resources in Yuexiu District Project (Project No.: FCZ2024-5039).

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